

Paleozoic near salt dome formations – a new target for EGS in Poland

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ABSTRACT

A new petroleum borehole and seismic data petroleum exploratory well, located close to the axial zone of the Mogilno-Łódź Trough (Polish Lowlands) delivered new insight into the local structural, tectonic, facial and thermal variability of this geological unit. For these purpose 3D model of Permian-Mesozoic strata have been prepared. This allows detailed structural mapping of the salt pillow-related Kłęcko anticline. Moreover, the resources assessment confined to the Rotliegend Enhanced Geothermal System (EGS) type reservoir, divided into the playa, eolian and fluvial facies-based complexes at depths of about 5000 m b.s.l. was performed. Using very conservative assumptions on the methods of the EGS reservoir development, authors assessed that unit heat in place and technical potential for eolian sandstones are about 386 PJ/km³ and ca. 2814 kW/km³, and for fluvial 367 PJ/km³, and ca. 2850 kW/km³, respectively. Moreover, the eolian complex is characterised by low shale content, influencing the high susceptibility to fracking. The presented research sheds light on new opportunities for further development of EGS in Rotliegend strata in central Poland, especially in the areas corresponding with over 100 salt structures mapped in Poland.

1. INTRODUCTION

Geothermal research started in the Polish Lowland over 40 years ago and has resulted in the discovery of two low-temperature prospecting reservoirs: Lower Cretaceous and Lower Jurassic located within Mogilno-Łódź Trough, Szczecin Trough and Warsaw Trough. Based on these results, seven geothermal district heating (GeoDH) projects are operational. One of the most prospective areas for the wide-range use of geothermal waters in the central part of the Polish Lowlands is the area of Mogilno-Łódź Trough (MLT). In our study, the site favourable for EGS system, located at MLT, north-east of Poznań city was investigated. In this area, the Lower Permian sandstones, claystones and mudstones representing playa, eolian and fluvial facies associations being possible target EGS reservoirs were examined. In 2019, in the study area, the K-1 oil exploration well was drilled. It identified a Zechstein salt pillow and provided valuable information about the geology including physical rock properties of Mesozoic and Permian strata. This enabled the re-evaluation and reinterpretation of vintage data combined with newly acquired data from K-1 well.

The K-1 well resulted in a unique data set for analysis of possible EGS utilization of the Rotliegend complex. The research comprises the structural and parametric (including temperature) 3D model. The model reflects regional variability based on a broad array of geophysical logs, including thermal logging from wells located within MLT, as well as in the marginal parts of surrounding Mid-Polish Swell (MPS) and Fore-Sudetic Monocline (FSM). Regional scale models of porosity, permeability, clay content and thermal parameters distribution derived from the petroleum geology (Zakrevsky, 2011; Papiernik, 2019) were reinterpreted in more detail considering the results of the new K-1 borehole drilling and 2D seismic interpretation in Kłęcko Anticline area as well. The modelling process results, supported by statistical analysis, indicate rather high geothermal prospectivity.

The performed detailed 3D geological modelling supplemented by the results of petrophysical laboratory measurements and statistical analysis shows that the Kłęcko Anticline could be the first EGS site in the Polish Lowlands, as the temperature in the most prospective eolian complex reaches 160°C, which confirms that significant potential for electricity generation exists here.

2. GEOLOGICAL AND GEOTHERMAL SETTING

The investigated area is located within the Mogilno-Łódź Trough (Karnkowski, 2008; Żelaźniewicz et al., 2011), a tectonic unit being part of the West and Central European Paleozoic Platform (WCEPP) margin, the zone comprising terranes such as the Trans-European Suture Zone (TESZ) or Brunovistulicum (Figure 1B) (Pożaryski, 1990; Guterch et al., 2010). This corresponds to the eastern extension of the Permian and Mesozoic system of epicontinental basins of Western and Central Europe – the Mid-Polish Trough (MPT) (Ziegler, 1990; Jarosiński et al., 2009).

According to the newest research, the Permian-Mesozoic architecture of MPT inherited its foundations after the Ediacaran rifting phase of Rodinia, which resulted in lithosphere thinning (Mazur et al, 2021). The direct impulse for the MPT development was the rifting phase in the latest Carboniferous to Early Permian, which was coupled with an intensive volcanic activity that was followed by post-rift thermal subsidence and the deposition of Lower Permian Rotliegend clastics and Zechstein marine. Thermal subsidence of the MPT continued up to the Late Cretaceous, involving three main pulses in: (1) Zechstein to Olenekian; (2) Oxfordian to Kimmeridgian; and (3) the Early Cenomanian deposits (Stephenson et al., 2003). The final stage of the MPT evolution was Late Turonian through Paleocene compressional inversion (Dadlez et al., 1995; Leszczyński, 2010). The MPT's inversion was a widespread uplift typical for basins with thick salt sequences. Inversion and subsequent erosion created the present-day structural

pattern of the Polish Lowlands, including the Fore-Sudetic Monocline, the Szczecin Trough, the Mogilno-Łódź-Miechów Trough, the Mid-Polish Swell (Anticlinorium) (MPS) and the North-Eastern Marginal Trough (Figure 1A) (Karnkowski, 2008; Żelaźniewicz et al., 2011; Narkiewicz & Dadlez, 2008). Regional subsidence patterns of the MPT locally were superimposed by salt movements that started in the Early Triassic (Krzywiec, 2012), resulting in a complex system of salt structures in the central and NW segments of the Polish Lowlands (Pożaryski, 1977). The final stage of the tectonic evolution of the Polish Lowlands involves Cenozoic Graben system development during the latest Eocene to Mid-Miocene times (Pharaoh et al., 2010; Jarosiński et al., 2009).

The MPT is underlain by 5–6 km thick complexes of Lower Paleozoic and Devonian-Carboniferous sediments (Dadlez et al., 1995). Permian-Mesozoic sedimentary successions of the MPT are, in general, continuous from the Rotliegend up to the Upper Cretaceous (Maastrichtian) strata, reaching a thickness of 8 km in the area close to East European Craton (EEC) (Marek & Pajchlowa (eds.), 1997); Doornenbal et al., 2010). Deposits of the Rotliegend group are represented by volcanic and terrigenous series, divided into numerous formal lithostratigraphic or allostratigraphic units (Pokorski, 2008). They can be correlated with those in the German part of the Southern Permian Basin (Gast et al., 2010). However, in petroleum exploration practice, terrigenous complexes of Permian in Poland are traditionally subdivided as non-reservoir Autunian and generally prospective Saxonian. The latter is represented by eolian and fluvial sandstones, playa mudstones and siltstones (Papiernik et al., 2010; Kiersnowski & Buniak, 2016). The maximum thickness of the Rotliegend continental clastic sediments in the MPT reaches 1400 m (Wagner et al., 2002).

Rotliegend deposits are covered by a Zechstein marine-carbonate and evaporite-cyclic sequence. In the MPT, it is represented by four evaporitic cycles, known as the Werra (Z1), the Stassfurt (Z2), the Leine (Z3), and the Aller (Z4), and in westernmost Poland by the youngest cycle, the Ohre (Z5) (Peryt et al., 2010; Dadlez et al., 2000). The original depositional thickness of the Zechstein probably reached up to 1500–2000 m in the MPT axial zone, gradually pinching out towards the basin margins (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Regional geology of the central part of Polish Lowlands: (A) Cenozoic subcrop map after Dadlez et al. (2000) – simplified; (B) Europe scale tectonic setting of the area of interest, based on Berthelsen (1992) – modified.

The internal part of the basin is, in general, dominated by salt facies, gradually re-placed at margins by sulfate and clastic ones. As a result of intensive salt movements (Triassic to Paleocene), the thickness of Zechstein in salt diapirs, in the Szczecin-Mogilno-Łódź Trough and the Mid-Polish Swell, locally reaches over 5000 m (Figure 2).

In the latest Permian to Anisian times, the evaporitic sabkha sedimentation of the uppermost Zechstein was replaced by continental – fluvial, lacustrine and playa deposits of the Buntsandstein, comprising three subgroups: Lower, Middle and Upper (Bachmann & Kozur, 2004). In regional mapping and petroleum exploration practice, deposits of the Lower Buntsandstein (LBS) and the Middle Buntsandstein sediments (MBS), because of their continental provenance, are referred to as Lower Triassic. The LBS deposits are mainly fluvial to lacustrine (Bachmann & Kozur, 2004) with marginal brackish intercalations (Pieńkowski, 1991). The MBS is composed of alternations of thin-bedded sandstones, siltstones and claystones of the playa and lacustrine origin. The thickness of the Lower Triassic complex in the Polish Lowlands is considerable and locally exceeds 1500 m.

Figure 2: Geological cross-section through the study area (Kz–Cenozoic, Cr2–Upper Cretaceous, Cr1-Tk–Lower Cretaceous Upper Triassic (Keuper), Pz–Zechstein, P1u–Upper Rotliegend, P1l–Lower Rotliegend, C2–Upper Carboniferous of the Hercynian Foredeep, C1–Lower Carboniferous of the Hercynian Foredeep, Cf–undivided folded Carboniferous of the Hercynian Orogenic Belt, bold line expresses the major faults).

The Middle Triassic in the MPT is represented by marine deposits. The succession starts with the Upper Buntsandstein strata (the equivalent of the *Röt Fm.*) represented by calcareous Röt dolomite and Röt kalk of southern Poland. It is also represented by a large brackish-water lagoon with predominantly fine-grained red clastics of a semi-closed evaporitic basin. They were gradually replaced by shallow sea carbonate sedimentation and the marine and hypersaline carbonates known as Muschelkalk (Bachmann et al. 2010).

The Upper Triassic of the MPT contains shale-dominated deposits of Ladinian through Rhaetian succession that is an equivalent of Keuper group (KG), which is divided into three subgroups. The Lower Keuper Subgroup (LKS) strata are represented predominantly by grey clastic deposits that were accumulated in various continental environments. The Middle Keuper Subgroup (MKS) was deposited mainly in ephemeral-lake and fluvial systems. The section of the MKS begins with evaporites and shales of the Lower Gipskeuper. They are covered by the Schliff Sandstein (*Stuttgart Fm.*) strata, which are dominated by fluvial plains to fluviodeltaic mudstones and sandstones (Marek & Pajchlowa, 1997). The next complex of the MKS is the Upper Gipskeuper strata (*Weser Fm.*), which are represented by evaporites of salina, sabkha or playa mudflats environments. The uppermost part of the MKS belongs to the Playa Arnstadt Formation (*Steinberger Keuper*). The uppermost Triassic (*Rhaetian*) deposits belong to the Upper Keuper Subgroup (UKS). They are the youngest part of the Triassic. In the MPT the UKS consists of non-marine fluvial and lacustrine deposits (Bachmann et al. 2010; Marek & Pajchlowa, 1997).

The Lower Jurassic (Hettangian to Toarcian) succession, starting from coarse-grained clastic sediments, predominantly consists of shallow-marine, brackish to fluviodeltaic provenance. The Lower Jurassic rocks are represented by the *Kamienna group*, which is subdivided into up to 12 formations (Pieńkowski, 2004). The Lower Jurassic strata reach thicknesses of up to 1300 m in the axial part of the MPT (Dadlez, 1998; Feldman-Olszewska, 1998).

The Middle Jurassic interval is represented by deposits of four stages – the Aalenian, Bajocian, Bathonian and Callovian. The MPT was partly isolated from the basins of western Europe during Aalenian and Bajocian times (Dadlez, 1998; Dayczak-Calikowska, 1998). Deposition in the MPT is characterized by marine clastic sedimentation in the uppermost part (Callovian) replaced by marine carbonates.

During the Late Jurassic, deposition was initially restricted to the axial parts of the MPT, and it was dominated in the north by clastic sedimentation (>800 m thick in the Pomeranian Basin). To the south, a transition to carbonate-dominated >1400 m thick, shelf sedimentation was observed (Niemczycka, Brochwicz-Lewiński, 1998). Starting in early Oxfordian times the deposition of marly mudstones, carbonate-cemented glauconitic sandstones and sponge-rich lime-mudstones (*Lyna Fm.*) was observed. Northwards it is interbedded with the *Chociwel Formation's* sandstones as well as limestones of the *Brda Fm.* in the central, western and northern parts of the Polish Lowlands (Lott et al., 2010). In the central part of the basin massive limestones, partially silicified, sponge-rich or dolomitized are dominant deposits. Within the upper Oxfordian strata, coral bioherms (*Coral Fm.*) are locally developed. Late Oxfordian-early Kimmeridgian strata were deposited in carbonate-shelf environments, replaced in Tithonian times by a restricted brackish basin, where Middle Tithonian limestones with shell beds gradually pass into anhydrites, dolomites and gypsum, ostracod-rich limestones, marls and sandstones of the upper Tithonian.

Cretaceous deposits survived mostly in the post-inversion troughs (Figure 1A). The Lower Cretaceous section in the Mogilno-Łódź Trough (MLT) is represented by the sandy deposits of Middle Albian, Barremian, Hauterivian, and Valanginian. The best reservoir interval comprises the *Mogilno Fm.* (Middle Albian through Barremian) represented by Pagórki Mb. (sandstones), Gopło Mb. (mudstones and sandstones) and Kruszwica Mb. (sandstones) (Leszczyński, 1997a). In the Polish Basin, Upper Cretaceous deposits represent six individual transgressive-regressive cycles (Leszczyński, 1997b). Generally, they were laid down in an open basin and shelf environment. In the MLT they are represented by associations of carbonate-siliceous, carbonate and marly lithofacies, often containing thick complexes of gaises and opokas (Leszczyński, 2010).

Lower Jurassic to Cretaceous successions in NW and SE Poland were subsequently removed by Upper Cretaceous–Paleocene inversion of the MPT to the Mid-Polish Swell (Figure 1A).

2.1. The geothermal setting of central and north-western Poland

Regional geothermal conditions of the Polish Lowlands have been a subject of research since the end of the 1980s, starting from the early works of Sokołowski (1998) through Górecki's series of geothermal atlases (Górecki (ed.), Hajto et al., 2006a;b; Hajto &

Górecki, 2010), up to an investigation on Enhanced Geothermal Systems (Sowizdżał et al., 2013). These works were followed by further regional and semi-regional projects conducted in 2020 by the AGH University of Science and Technology. These projects introduced a new quantitative approach based on 3D static models (Kępińska et al. 2017; Sowizdżał et al., 2020) that applied modified workflows elaborated for petroleum exploration as well as Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) purposes (Papiernik & Michna, 2019).

In the Polish Lowlands, most geothermal aquifers are commonly represented by siliciclastic rocks, mainly sandstones, in which the geothermal potential, apart from temperature, is controlled by petrophysical rock properties, mainly intergranular effective porosity and intrinsic permeability. These parameters strongly depend not only on sedimentology and petrography but are strongly influenced by the chemical composition of formation waters and the temperature. Other factors that affected reservoir quality were also compaction and inversion episodes related to tectonic evolution.

All geothermal aquifers of the Polish Lowlands can be classified as conduction-dominated geothermal plays. Regarding the considerable similarity of the geology between the Polish and German parts of the Southern Permian Basin, play classifications (Moeck & Beardsmore, 2014) derived in Germany can be applied. It allows identifying within the Polish Lowlands two types of geothermal plays – Intracratonic Basin (CD1 Plays) and Crystalline Rock Basement (CD3 Plays in Figure 3). In this case, CD3 Plays type is represented by sedimentary EGS plays (Tester et al., 2006; Moeck, 2014). The CD1 Plays in Poland represent commercially developed reservoirs of the Lower Jurassic and the Lower Cretaceous. CD3 Plays are, in Poland, only a subject of theoretical considerations, which allowed identification, in the Kuiavian segment of the Mid-Polish Swell, a possible sedimentary EGS play, in low porosity and low permeability sedimentary rocks of Lower and Middle Buntsandstein (Sowizdżał et al., 2013) as well as in volcanic covers of Autunian in the western part of the Fore-Sudetic Monocline. In these works, Rotliegend deposits were also qualified as possibly favourable for EGS development, but they have not yet been recognized in detail.

Figure 3: Compilation of operational geothermal sites in Poland, the main petrophysical parameters based on the geothermal play types (CD1–Intracratonic Basin Play type, CD2–Foreland Basin Play type, CD3–Crystalline Basement Play type, based on Moeck (2014), simplified).

Considering subsurface thermal conditions in Poland, in general, the Polish Lowlands are characterized by low to moderate heat flow values (HF). According to different research, HF values range from ca. 30 to 110 mW/m² (Szewczyk & Gientka, 2009; Nawrocki & Becker (Eds.), 2017) and from ca. 30 to 90 mW/m² (Majorowicz & Wybraniec, 2011; Majorowicz, Polkowski & Grad, 2019; Majorowicz, Grad & Polkowski, 2019) – more likely. Consequently, an average geothermal gradient varies from 1 to ca. 3.8°C/100 m (Szewczyk et al., 2006).

The Polish Lowlands can be divided into two basic thermal provinces: the relatively cold Precambrian EEC and the relatively warm WCEPP (Figure 1). Usually, HF in the EEC area is below 55 mW/m², whereas in WCEPP it is distinctly higher and more diversified, reaching from <55 to >80 mW/m². The highest heat flow values have been noticed from northwestern Poland in the area of the Fore-Sudetic Monocline, within an approximately 50–70 km wide belt. This zone corresponds to the trend of continental crust thinning (Majorowicz & Šafanda, 2018). The zone of the highest HF corresponds to the location of the thick (up to 1000 m) volcanic cover of Autunian, but their quantitative relationships have not yet been recognized. In the area of the MLT two operating GeoDH plants are located in the towns of Uniejów and Poddębice. Both of them use geothermal waters from a Lower Cretaceous aquifer (Hajto & Górecki, 2010a;b; Sowizdżał et al., 2020). The most recent geothermal project, located close to the study area, is the Konin GT-1 geothermal well, drilled in 2015 to a total depth of 2660 m.

During the testing, the water temperature at the well-head reached 92°C, which is the highest value reported from Poland. The temperature of thermal brines at the bottom of the Lower Jurassic reservoir reaches 97.5°C. The well productivity has been determined as 114 m³/h. All the above-mentioned geothermal projects have been focused on reserves accumulated in Mesozoic hydrothermal aquifers. The geothermal potential of Paleozoic formations has still not been unlocked. Detailed operating parameters of the heating plant in the Mogilno-Łódź Basin are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: The main operating parameters of the geothermal installations in Mogilno-Łódź Trough.

Location	Aquifer	Well-head Temperature	Admissible Water Productivity	Water Mineralization	Installed Geothermal Capacity	Total Installed Capacity (Geothermal + Peak Load)	Annual Heat Production
		°C	m ³ /h	g/dm	MW _t	MW _t	TJ/a
Podębnice	Lower	71	252	0.4	10.0	10.0	63
Uniejów	Cretaceous	68	120	6-8	3.4	7.4	9

Recognized analogues for Paleozoic geothermal prospects within the Polish Permian Basin can be found in the Northeastern German Basin. Both basins combined form one huge Pan-European structure called the Central European Basin, where a significant geothermal potential is being reported (Weber et al., 2015). The best known geothermal installations located in the central-north part of Germany are Groß Schönebeck (with 150°C at 3830–4250 m b.g.l.), with Rotliegend tight sandstone and andesites (Blöcher et al., 2016; 83. Zimmermann et al., 2009), Neustadt-Glewe (with 98°C at 2195–2300 m b.g.l., and productivity of 100 m³/h) and Waren (Müritz) (with 63°C at 1540 m b.g.l., and productivity of 60 m³/h) within the Rhaetian sandstone reservoir (Franz et al., 2018).

The studies on EGS geothermal plays, including the Polish experience and specific geological conditions, allowed to elaborate the criteria for the development of a commercial geothermal plant in a low permeability and porosity reservoir (Tester et al., 2006; Jupe et al., 1995; Huenges et al., 2007; Sausse, 2007; Brown et al., 2012; Lu, 2018).

The K-1 well is located close to the axis of the western part of the Mogilno-Łódź Trough, on the northern slope of the significant positive HF anomaly of the Fore-Sudetic Monocline. According to legacy data, HF value at K-1 location varies about 85 mW/m² (as mentioned earlier), while the estimated temperature at the top of the Rotliegend was approximated as about 139°C, at a depth of ca. 4300 m b.s.l., and thermal gradient ca. 2.9°C/100 m. So far, rather sedimentary Lower Triassic deposits were suggested as more EGS system-ready than the Rotliegend one in the Polish Lowland (Sowizdzal et al., 2013). However, the above comparison to the German Basin and the inspection of basic requirements, which should be satisfied to locate the EGS plant (Table 2), speaks for possible increased prospects for K-1 region.

Table 2: Compilation of criteria conditioning preliminary selection of geological structure for EGS based on a literature review.

Parameter	Quantitative criteria	Source of information
	<i>Major Criteria</i>	
Reservoir depth	5–6 km	Potter et al., 1972; Williams et al., 2008
	4–6 km	Wójcicki et al., 2013
Reservoir thickness	≥200 m	Wójcicki et al., 2013
	≥300 m	Bujakowski et al., 2015
Reservoir rock temperature	90°C (minimum temperature for electric power production)	Williams et al., 2008
	>100°C (enough for heat production for GEODH or moderate for binary cycle electricity production)	Tester et al., 2006; Huenges et al., 2007
	>150°C (effective electricity production)	Tester et al., 2006; Jupe et al., 1995
Initial permeability	The lower the better (<3 mD)	Pazdro & Kozerski, 1990
Effective porosity of the rock mass	The lower the better (<3%)	Wójcicki et al., 2013
Caprock thickness	>20 m	according to CCS requirements (Chadwick et al., 2008)
<i>Minor criteria</i>		
Thermo-physical parameters of the reservoir rocks	High thermal conductivity and high specific heat of reservoir rock	Tester et al., 2006; Jupe et al., 1995; Huenges et al., 2007
Circulation flow rate	30 l s ⁻¹ (ca. 108 m ³ /h)	Jupe et al., 1995
	50–75 kg s ⁻¹ (ca. 180–270 m ³ /h)	Barbier, 2002
	50–100 kg s ⁻¹ (ca. 180–360 m ³ /h)	Garnish et al., 1992; Rybach, 2010
	50–100 l s ⁻¹ (ca. 180–360 m ³ /h)	Jung, 2013; Breede et al., 2013
Rock volume accessed	>2 · 10 ⁸ m ³ = 0.2 km ³	McDermott et al., 2006; Butler et al., 2004
Effective heat transfer area	>2 · 10 ⁶ m ²	Barbier, 2002

Other minors but also important factors in deciding on the EGS location are:

- Resistance to water saturation, especially resistivity to swelling, generally going along with the low clay content;
- Susceptibility to massive fracturing;
- Lack or very weak inflow of groundwater into EGS system;
- Maximum allowable reservoir temperature drawdown during the operation – 10%;
- Low flow losses in the EGS system – below 10% of injection flow.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The case presented in this paper is an example of a quantitative assessment of local geothermal conditions, disclosed with the results of the new deep well. The K-1 well completion has given a new look into the geological and thermal conditions of the central part of the Mogilno-Łódź Trough. Logging and coring enabled advanced core-based analysis. The latter was completed on samples of Rotliegend rocks from the interval of 4585.15 to 5180.35 m b.g.l.

Thermal conductivity (TC) measurements were carried out in steady-state conditions on 5 samples of mudstone, sandstone and vulcanite rocks taken from the Rotliegend interval of K-1 well. The measurements were completed using FOX50–190 LaserComp device on dry samples in the temperature range 152–168°C, corresponding to reservoir conditions. The measured TC values are variable in the range of 1.125 (mudstone) to 2.906 W/m K (sandstone). TC of vulcanite rocks at a depth of 5180.35 m was estimated at 2.134 W/m K. Moreover, to test the resistance of target reservoir rocks to hydraulic fracturing the LST tests were performed. The test showed that the examined rocks slightly swell under the influence of FFS under high pressure (1500-2000 psi) and high temperature (160-170°C). The observed swelling values vary in the range of 4.6-8%.

Log-based interpretations are of crucial importance in the process of spatial geomodeling. Borehole logging enables both stratigraphic interpretation and quantitative description of petrophysical, lithological and physical parameters of depositional sequences. In the study, results of industrial volumetric interpretation of basic rock components (quartz, calcite, dolomite, anhydrite, halite, clay minerals) as well as water and gas saturation from many wells were used (the results are not presented here). The very recent completion of the K-1 well allowed for reliable estimation of the thermal conductivity logs, using commonly described methods (Brigaud et al., 1990; Demongodin et al., 1991; Midttømme, 1997; Hartmann et al., 2005; Gąsior & Przelaskowska, 2014; Hajto et al., 2020), that in the Rotliegend interval were calibrated with laboratory measurements. Available data allowed us to apply a mixing law model to calculate bulk TC for the whole drilled section using textbook TC values (Figure 4).

Following the experience of previous authors (Woodside & Messmer, 1961; Sass et al., 1971; Brigaud & Vasseur, 1989; Tatar et al., 2020) analysis, the geometric mean model, originally introduced by Lichtenecker (1931) was used to calculate the saturated bulk TC. The thermal conductivity of the selected rock's components and reservoir media used for the calculations performed in the study are shown in Figure 4. Because of a lack of appropriate data, the correction for pressure was not considered.

Figure 4: Thermal conductivity of selected rock components and reservoir media (according to Plewa (1994), Hajto et al., (2020), Brigaud & Vasseur (1989), Tatar et al. (2020), Horai & Simmons (1969), Horai (1971), Čermák & Rybach (1982), Plewa, S. (1966), Pasquale et al. (2017), Robertson (1988) – blue bars express thermal conductivity values of particular rock type and media used for the calculations performed in the study).

In the K-1 well the thermal logging was performed in the perturbed conditions in several runs. The logs were combined into a composite, standardized to the quasi-equilibrium conditions with the application of the method described by Kudrewicz (2021), and calibrated by DST results. The standardized composite log was then used for the determination of the thermal gradient log, which was computed by a differentiation of the thermal log. The characterization of thermal parameters was extended by computation of the heat flow (HF), as well as radiogenic heat (RH) logs. In the case of conductive flow, the basis for the calculation of heat flow value is the depth-related rate of temperature changes observed in the wells analyzed together with thermal conductivity. The mathematical expression describing the relationships between the above-mentioned values is Fourier's (1822; 1824) equation:

$$Q = -k \cdot \nabla T \quad (1)$$

Where Q , k , ∇T are heat flow [W/m²], thermal conductivity [W/m K] and thermal gradient [K/m], respectively.

RH log reflects radiogenic heat produced by the rocks. In the described case, it has been assessed in K-1 well, based on the Bückner & Rybach [150] formula that is related to natural gamma rays directly:

$$A = 0.0158 \cdot (GR - 0.8) \quad (2)$$

Where A , GR are radiogenic heat [μ W/m³] and natural gamma ray [API], respectively.

3.1. Spatial Interpretation

Contemporary 3D static geological models created for geothermal or petroleum exploration purposes tend to be multiscale solutions that can be used in resolving regional to local scale exploration problems (Papiernik & Michna, 2019; Papiernik et al., 2010; Demongodin et al., 1991). Models can be invaluable for integrating, understanding and supporting petroleum and geothermal field decisions (Ringrose & Bentley, 2015).

For the preliminary resource assessment of HDR/EGS system in the study area spatial modelling with the use of Petrel software has been implemented. Before the completion of the K-1 well, the prediction of the structural, facies and petrophysical variability in this region was based on regional trends. Only 13 wells deeper than 500 m, but not reaching the top of Middle Buntsandstein, and results of the regional seismic lines ZRG00897 and ZRG00997 interpretation (Wagner et al., 2002) (Figure 5) were located within the structural model. Well logs from these wells do not contain data suitable for thermal or petrophysical analysis. Such a situation resulted in the necessity of regional trend extrapolation at the K-1 well vicinity. To gain this objective, the authors primarily build a temporary structural model covering the MLT, the northern part of FSM and the southern part of the MPS. The input data set used for the construction of the structural model were regional structural maps of particular stages in interval base Cenozoic through top Devonian, prepared and systematically developed by an AGH University of Science and Technology team (Górecki (ed.), Hajto et al., 2006a; b; Doornenbal et al., 2010; Kępińska et al., 2017). Then, this geometrical framework was used to prepare a regional scale parametric model. The large area of the regional framework covers quite a considerable quantity of input data (Table 3).

Table 3. Input data for parametric modelling in a structural framework.

Permeability PERM	Porosity PHI	Shale Volume VSH	Bulk Density RHOB	Temperature °C
99	108	85	38	56

Most of the input data have been collected during the preparation of geothermal atlases (Górecki (ed.), Hajto et al., 2006a;b), and regional analysis of hydrocarbon potential of the Rotliegend in Poland (Papiernik et al., 2010). A small amount of borehole data has been acquired for geothermal exploration. Most of the deep wells were designed for hydrocarbon exploration, and they are rarely located to the north of the FSM. The closest deep wells that have reached the top of Rotliegend are: Września IG-1, Środa IG-2, Objezierze IG-1, G-2, Czeszewo IG-1, Bygoszcz IG-1, Piła IG-1, and B-1. They are located in the area of the MLT, MPS or FSM, and they have been used in the modelling of temperature, VSH and PHI. Other, not distant, wells used in the modelling of shallower complexes were, e.g., Swarzędz IGH-1, Wągrowiec IG-1, and Cykowo IG-1. Using that kind of framework, working regional parametric models of temperature (TEMP), porosity (PHI), shale volume (VSH) and bulk density (RHOB) were constructed. Then local modifications were introduced as a result of K-1 well completion, and interpretation of the new seismic data acquired in this area (Figure 5).

Figure 5. The structural and parametric model of the research area

This modelling disclosed very complex tectonic settings of the area – different for pre-Zechstein, Zechstein and post-Permian strata. Geological layers were modelled directly by using an unstructured tetrahedral mesh, which is internally constrained by faults (Papiernik & Michna, 2019; Souche et al., 2013). The second stage of modelling comprises the application of the SF method and SF to CPG conversion. Preliminary parametric models although locally fitted to K-1 were externally controlled (trended) by regional parametric models, using multiscale modelling workflows.

4. EGS RESOURCE ASSESSMENT

A preliminary geothermal resource assessment of the target Rotliegend EGS was carried out using the volumetric method. It relies mostly on the assessment of the volume mass of rocks and accompanying heat stored therein (heat in place – HIP). The volumetric method is often used to provide estimates of the probable electrical generation capacity of a geothermal system.

Apart from the assessment of theoretical potential (relating to annual mean ambient temperature – T_0), also technical potential has been taken into account. Technical potential includes, among others, the estimation of the recoverable fraction (recovery factor – R) of reserves suitable for utilization from a technical point of view. The assessment of technical reserves, unlike theoretical ones, requires among others determination of the heat utilization technology, including heat and/or power production. Moreover, the recovery factor also depends on the efficiency of the thermodynamic cycle, the minimum operating temperature, the production temperature and the output, the re-injection temperature and others. A simplified division of the geothermal potential classes is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Division of the geothermal potential classes – from theoretical to realistic, based on Van Wees et al., (2013), Trumpy et al., (2016), modified.

The principles of the volumetric method of HDR/EGS resource and reserves assessment have been broadly discussed in many publications for decades (Williams et al., 2008; Van Wees et al., 2010; 2013; Sowizdzal et al., 2013; Blackwell et al., 2006; Beardsmore et al., 2010; Limberger et al., 2014; Chamorro et al., 2014; Feng et al., 2014). The methodology taking into account environmental and economic considerations has been also the subject of many projects and research work. The best-known practices and approaches consider among the other:

- Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) Interdisciplinary Panel (Tester et al., 2006);
- Canadian Geothermal Code for Public Reporting, by the CGC Committee (Deibert et al., 2010);
- A Protocol for Estimating and Mapping Global EGS Potential (Beardsmore et al., 2010);
- New Geothermal Terms and Definitions – the Geothermal Energy Association (GEA, 2010);
- Resource Assessment Protocol for GEO-ELEC (Van Wees et al., 2011);
- United Nations Framework Classification for Fossil Energy and Mineral Reserves and Resources 2009 (UNFC-2009) (UNECE, 2016).

For this study, the methodology and approach developed in the GEO-ELEC project (Van Wees et al., 2013) were employed. The lack of detailed information on the market conditions of geothermal electricity production and other shortages meant that economic issues were not taken into account. Therefore, this study focuses solely on the assessment of theoretical and technical potential according to the definitions given by Rybach (2010), Van Wees et al., (2013) and Beardsmore (2010).

4.1. Theoretical Potential of EGS

The theoretical potential (E_{th}) of the K-1 structure was calculated according to the Rybach's (2010) definition and Equation (3).

Heat in place (HIP) is defined as total heat stored in rock mass volume, including rock matrix, formation fluids, and reservoir temperature. In EGS systems, due to assumed low effective porosity, fluid heat content is negligible:

$$HIP = V \cdot \rho_{rock} \cdot c_{rock} \cdot (T_{prod} - T_0) \cdot 10^{-15} \quad (3)$$

Where HIP , V , ρ_{rock} , c_{rock} , T_{prod} , T_0 are heat in place [PJ], reservoir volume [m^3], rock density [kg/m^3], specific heat of reservoir rock [$J/kg \cdot K$], reservoir temperature at the midpoint [$^{\circ}C$], annual mean ambient air temperature [$^{\circ}C$] ($T_0 = 8^{\circ}C$).

The resulting HIP can be used to determine the theoretical potential for geothermal energy production considering realistic recovery factors and efficiency of standard geothermal power plants (Organic Rankine and Kalina Cycle).

Theoretical capacity (TC) is calculated as the heat in place multiplied by a conversion factor which depends on the mode of utilization. Theoretical capacity (Equation 4 and 5) takes into account that energy cannot be utilized until the surface temperature (T_0). A return temperature (T_r), according to Williams et al. (2008) and Beardsmore et al. (2010), equal the cut-off temperature for the electricity production. For the study location $T_0 = 8^{\circ}C$, thus $T_r = T_0 + 80^{\circ}C = 88^{\circ}C$.

$$TC = HIP_e \cdot \eta_{th} \quad (4)$$

Where TC , HIP_e , η_{th} are theoretical capacity (PJ), effective heat in place (J) and cycle thermal efficiency for power conversion (–) respectively. Effective heat in place (HIP_e) can be expressed by the following Equation (5) after Van Wees et al. (2013) and Beardsmore et al. (2010):

$$HIP_e = V \cdot \rho_{rock} \cdot c_{rock} \cdot (T_{prod} - T_r) \cdot 10^{-15} \quad (5)$$

Where HIP_e , V , ρ_{rock} , c_{rock} , T_{prod} , T_r are effective heat in place (PJ), reservoir volume (m^3), rock density (kg/m^3), specific heat of reservoir rock ($J/kg \cdot K$), reservoir temperature at the midpoint ($^{\circ}C$), the cut-off production temperature for the electricity, equal to the temperature to which the crust can theoretically be reduced through the utilization of geothermal heat (assumed $T_r = 88^{\circ}C$), (10^{-15}) means conversion factor from J to PJ.

According to Beardsmore et al. (2010), cycle thermal efficiency is plant-dependent, even for the same inlet fluid temperature. The design and arrangement of specific plant components may include a trade-off between cost and efficiency. Cycle thermal efficiency, η_{th} , is a function of reservoir temperature and can be expressed by Tester et al.'s (2006) formula, so since T_{prod} denotes the average reservoir temperature, η_{th} can be expressed with the following formula (Equation 6):

$$\eta_{th} = 0.00052 \cdot T_{prod} + 0.032 \quad (6)$$

Where η_{th} , T_{prod} are cycle thermal efficiency for power conversion (–) and reservoir temperature at the midpoint ($^{\circ}C$) respectively.

4.2. Technical Potential of EGS

Technical potential denotes the expected recoverable geothermal energy (MW) after Williams et al. (2008) and Van Wees et al. (2013). The technical potential (TP) assumes that the reserves will be utilized for a period of 30 years (life span of power generation equals $9.46 \cdot 10^8$ s). The conversion from the theoretical capacity (TC) to technical potential (TP) is therefore Equation (7):

$$TP = 1.057 \cdot TC \cdot R \quad (7)$$

Where TP , TC , R are technical potential [MW_e/km^2], theoretical capacity [PJ/km^2], recovery factor (0–1) and 1.057 means conversion factor from PJ to MW, considering 30-years life span.

The recovery factor (R) is the portion of heat that can ultimately be recovered from a volume of rock. The formula of recovery factor determination for the purpose of power production with EGS was the subject of in-depth studies [69,97,131,133,136]. All the above indicates that (R) depends on many theoretical assumptions, including reservoir, technical and environmental issues such as fractured volume of rock, permeability, and rock temperature, which are not possible to quantify at the early stage of the project like that currently being studied.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Analytical and modelling works completed for K-1 derived data provided for this study resulted in several types of products: calibration data, input data for modelling, complex geological interpretation, and potential assessment. The thermal conductivity measured by the FOX50–190 apparatus provided values of 2.821–2.906 W/m K for sandstones, 1.125–2.379 W/m K for claystones and 2.134 W/m K for volcanic rocks (Figure 4). Based on methods described in previous sections, thermal gradient, thermal conductivity, and radiogenic heat production logs for the entire drilled interval were calculated, which allowed for the heat flux estimation.

The thermal gradient, determined for the entire drilled interval, varies along the well axis from 0.89 to 7.31 $^{\circ}C/100$ m with an average value of 2.9 $^{\circ}C/100$ m. The TC value varies from 0.95 W/m K (claystone) to 5.52 W/m K (evaporates). Radiogenic heat production varies from 0.16 to 7.07 $\mu W/m^3$. Heat flow density was assessed as 83.85 mW/m², with a negligible share of radiogenic heat at a level of 1.13%. The variability of these parameters for the Rotliegend interval is illustrated in Figure 4 and varies: the thermal gradient from 1.07 to 4.10 $^{\circ}C/100$ m, thermal conductivity from 1.13 to 3.79 W/m K, and radiogenic heat from 0.45 to 4.39 $\mu W/m^3$.

These results together with remaining local and regional data were also used in the preparation of both structural 3D and parametric models of the investigated area. For the purpose of geological interpretation of the near Kłeczek Salt Anticline area 13 wells deeper than 500 m, and results of the regional seismic lines ZRG00897 and ZRG00997 were considered (Figure 5).

According to this interpretation, the Kłeczek Anticline is a broad, NE-SW oriented fold (brachyanticline), developed over the Zechstein salt pillow, in the Mesozoic strata. It is cut along its axis by a normal fault extending from the Zechstein top up to the Cenozoic base. Its geometry is weakly controlled by seismic data.

The decision on K-1 spudding followed the very recent completion, as well as partial merge and reprocessing of three 2D seismic surveys, which comprised 24 seismic lines. Based on these data, a structural and tectonic reinterpretation was completed by the PGNiG Team. As a result, a large antiformal structure on the top surface of the Rotliegend complex was discovered. The K-1 well outcomes resulted in further changes in the understanding of the local geology, as at its bottom, volcanic rocks of Autunian were found. Analysis of the results of the regional geothermal modelling shows that in the vicinity of the K-1 well, the heat flow density value may reach up to ca. 84 mW/m² and the temperature at a depth of 4000 m b.g.l. around 130 $^{\circ}C$.

To prepare 3D structural model a tectonic interpretation of the pre-Zechstein basement has been conducted. These data were supplemented with the new tectonic interpretation of the Zechstein complex, as the authors suggested the presence of a series of intra-salt thrusts that developed in the eastern wing of the Kłeczek structure (probably they also exist in the western flank of the salt pillow but to a minor extent). In addition, the tectonic setting of the Mesozoic cover was reinterpreted for modeling purposes. It involves large faults that form a complex tectonic graben system (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Structural interpretation of the Kłecko anticline (D–Devonian, C–Carboniferous, Pr–Rotliegend, Prv–Rotliegend volcanites, Prf–Rotliegend fluvial deposits, Pre–Rotliegend eolian deposits, Prp–Rotliegend playa, Pz–Zechstein, T1–Lower Triassic (Buntsandstein), T2–Middle Triassic (Muschelkalk), Tk–Keuper, T3–Upper Triassic, J1–Lower Jurassic, J2–Middle Jurassic, J3–Upper Jurassic, Cr1–Lower Cretaceous, Cr2–Upper Cretaceous, Kz–Cenozoic).

According to the thickness and structural variability, the Mesozoic fault system originated during the Late Cretaceous, post-Albian times. The graben involving all Mesozoic strata was formed over the salt pillow’s crest in a transtensional regime, resulting from the compressional deformation of underlying Zechstein salts. This late Cretaceous compression led to the development of the salt pillow and the gradual elevating of the eastern wing of the Kłecko Anticline. That process resulted in the erosion that created spatially restricted Albian subcrops below the Cenozoic base, east of the marginal fault of the Kłecko Graben (Figure 7).

The K-1 well is distant from other wells in the central part of the Mogilno–Łódź Trough, and it gives new stratigraphic control of that area. On the other hand, it is located in a very specific place, within the tectonic graben, and over the salt pillow. The stratigraphic column revealed by K-1 seems to be quite concordant with previous predictions for the Middle Jurassic to Upper Cretaceous strata. In general, it is also consistent with the assumptions regarding the Rotliegend successions. A considerable difference in the Permian interval is the unpredicted occurrence of volcanic rocks, which are located further to the east than previously mapped (Doornenbal et al., 2010; Papiernik et al., 2010). The shape and the thickness of the salt pillow also differ considerably from the older assumptions. The Lower Buntsandstein deposits drilled in K-1 are probably not representative of the zone, as the eastern marginal fault of the Kłecko Graben causes a reduction of the Lower and Middle Buntsandstein sequences.

The stratigraphic column of the K-1 well, together with the new structural model, delivers not only a new stratigraphic control over the area but also gives novel insight into its thermal and petrophysical variability. Completed models revealed a considerable discrepancy between regional approximations and final models locally improved by K-1 results. They can be the result of small-scale anomalies of the thermal field over the Autunian volcanic massive and/or the salt pillow of Zechstein, as well as of the geological evolution of the Kłecko Graben. Using models of shale volume (VSH), temperature (TEMP), temperature gradient and radiogenic heat production the authors illustrate the nature of the local anomalies compared to regional variability (Figures 8-10).

Figure 8. Spatial illustration of modeling results: model of shale volume (VSH)

Figure 9. Distribution of geothermal gradient along the NW–SE cross-section

Figure 10. Distribution of the radiogenic heat production along the NW–SE cross-section

Temperature is a specific parameter, which shows smooth, wide-radius and depth-dependent spatial variability (Figure 11). The actual temperature in K-1 at particular depths is about 15°C higher than expected before the completion of the drilling, but its spatial variability is highly anomalous also due to local geology. The temperature distribution model shows an abrupt temperature rise over the salt pillow crest and in the hanging wall of the Klecko Graben. Such variability demonstrates, on one side, high influence of the salt on the thermal field in its overburden, and on the other one, it can imply the very young age of the salt structure and the graben. Approximately 10 km to the west from the eastern limit of the graben, the top of the Rotliegend and temperature decrease to the average regional trend (Figure 11).

Figure 11. Distribution of the temperature along the NW–SE cross-sections

The results of quantitative modelling show the variability of the main petrophysical and thermal properties in the vicinity of K-1 borehole (Table 4). Eolian and fluvial complexes show much better thermal conditions in the local model compared to the regional approximation that was in use before drilling the K-1 borehole.

Table 4. Basic statistics of modelled parameters derived from 3D model (min–max, avg.)

Parameter	Playa	Eolian	Fluvial
PHI (%)	0.43–3.19 (1.19)	0.00–8.85 (4.90)	0.26–3.70 (1.76)
Vsh (%)	0.21–66.87 (32.44)	9.58–66.69 (22.49)	35.45–72.84 (60.97)
RHOB (g/cm ³)	2.58–2.77 (2.69)	2.50–2.69 (2.58)	2.26–2.86 (2.58)
Temp (°C)	135.39–161.59 (152.31)	150.75–170.07 (160.84)	160.62–172.83 (166.34)
Thermal gradient (°C/100 m)	1.56–2.43 (2.08)	1.10–4.17 (2.83)	3.21–3.42 (3.37)
Radiogenic heat (μW/m ³)	0.32–1.65 (1.27)	0.64–1.90 (0.89)	1.25–3.24 (1.85)

The remaining modelled parameters show different, more geology-dependent, variability characteristics that represent rather planar trends, without obvious vertical constituents. Presented discrepancies clearly illustrate the general tendency of the regional model's limitations, as, despite stochastic methods application, the forecasts of PHI and VSH were overestimated at the K-1 location.

Porosity models of Rotliegend again disclose that the regional forecast was too optimistic. While in general, the vertical layout of porous and nonporous layers in both variants is similar, the quantitative description of PHI differs even more than 50% for all distinguished complexes.

Another parameter used in geothermal analyses is the bulk density of rocks (RHOB), which is related to the lithology, porosity and burial depth of sedimentary rocks. The variability of RHOB is demonstrated in Table 4.

Geothermal parameters of Rotliegend complexes in Kłeczek Anticline for EGS system based on a 3D modelling and literature review, combined with the results of the preliminary potential assessment are shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Geothermal parameters of Rotliegend complexes in Kłeczek Anticline for EGS system based on a 3D modelling and literature review, combined with the results of the preliminary potential assessment.

Complex	Th m	V x 10 ⁸ m ³	ρ _{rock} g/cm ³	C _{rock} J/kg·K	T _{prod} °C	η _{th} x 10 ⁻²	HIP PJ	HIP _e PJ	TC PJ	TP _{th} MW _e	TP _{real} kW _e	TP _{low} kW _e
Playa	232.10	2.00	2.69	890	152	11.12	69.10	30.79	3.42	3.62	452.42	36.19
Eolian	334.25	2.88	2.58	980	161	11.56	111.30	53.04	6.13	6.48	810.44	64.84
Fluvial	326.31	2.81	2.58	900	166	11.85	103.38	51.15	6.06	6.41	800.80	64.06

Temperature gradient and radiogenic heat production have been spatially reconstructed using K-1 well logs. These parameters add very precious information to the local characteristics of the structure. At the base of the Kłeczek Anticline, a significant decrease in thermal gradient (Figure 9) and an increase in temperature (Figure 11) are observed.

Similar behaviour of these parameters has been described from almost all types of salt structures, except for salt pillows, from the German part of the Polish-German Permian Basin (Szyperko-Teller & Moryc, 1998). Practically in all structures analyzed by this team, isotherms at the base of the structure tend upwards. The maximum amplitude is located more or less in the centre of the structure. An increase in temperature and a decrease in the thermal gradient at the base of salt structures is a direct consequence of the high thermal conductivity of salts. In the topmost Playa complex, a cooling effect is observed. It is probably responsible for the surprisingly low temperatures approximated for the Playa complex as well (Table 5). Complexes located below Playa display a very stable and rather high-temperature gradient of ca. 3.5°C/100 m.

Within the Rotliegend sequence in the interval corresponding to the Fluvial facies, a noticeable increase of radiogenic heat (>3.2 μW/m²) is observed (Figure 10). It is a direct result of an increase in natural gamma radioactivity (up to 260 API), which is expressed also in high values of interpreted VSH (up to 72%). In general, the Rotliegend Playa facies within the Polish Permian Basin do not show such high clay volumes (Papiernik et al., 2010). In the case of the Kłeczek Anticline, an increase in gamma-ray and radiogenic heat has to be caused by the rise of uranium content. The most probable explanation for this fact is an important fraction of volcanic rocks weathering products in the total mass of Playa facies rocks.

Due to the lack of appropriate core material, further attempts of explanation are more or less speculative, but the sequence may contain some tuff or tuffite intercalations. The concentration of minerals containing radioactive isotopes does not have to be a residuum of weathering of volcanic rocks building direct bedrock. It may also contain products of fluvial sedimentation or result from flooding events and related to their concentration of heavy minerals of volcanic origin.

The parameters and considerations presented above were then used in the volumetric assessment of geothermal potential. They indicate that the Eolian complex in the K-1 area is an optimal one for the development of the EGS-type geothermal field.

5.1. Preliminary Results of EGS Geothermal Potential Assessment

A case study presented in this paper assumes the production of electricity, although combined heat and power (CHP) installation can also be considered. For the management and utilization of a geothermal reservoir following the objectives, the relevant reservoir temperature and sufficiently high production rates of geothermal fluids should at least be ensured. Although the article does not

address any issues related to the technology of heat extraction from the carrier fluid, the authors assume that the system will meet the cut-off criteria given in the literature for the initial economic viability of the EGS (Potter et al., 1972; Williams et al., 2008). This applies to a minimum fluid circulation rate of approx. 144 m³/h and a minimum working fluid temperature of approx. 160°C. To obtain such high productivity, the permeability of the supposed reservoir has to be stimulated by hydraulic fracturing. The hydraulic conductivity of the reservoir is determined by the rock mass permeability, which should be dominated by the fracture system rather than by low matrix permeability, estimated at 0.04 mD (an average value for the Rotliegend in the K-1 well).

In the model of heat exchange between the injected fluids and the rock mass, the parameters and shape of the zone that would be fractured were assumed. This zone defines a space for the accumulation of fluid migration between the wells and would be limited by poorly permeable or impermeable formations with a permeability of 0.04 mD. The fractured zone is vertically limited by the rock properties and laterally by the extent of the fracture. The assumed calculation reservoir has the shape of a cuboid with a total volume presented in Table 5.

The quantitative analysis focused on the determination of the amount of heat and/or power that can be produced from K-1 and requires an extensive multivariate analysis including reservoir simulations and modelling. This should be the subject of further work leading to a precise assessment of technical reserves through the preparation of the feasibility study verifying the economic viability of the heat production from the K-1 EGS geothermal field.

For the preliminary calculation of technical potential, it is proposed to apply a simplified approach taking into account three different levels of R expressing: theoretical, realistic and pessimistic scenarios for geothermal energy extraction from the K-1 reservoir (Blackwell et al., 2006; Limberger et al., 2014):

- TP_{theory} – the maximum possible (theoretical) technical potential ($R = 1.00$);
- TP_{real} – realistic underground technical potential according to typical predictive reservoir engineering approaches and empirical practice expressing the mean value of recovery factor ($R = 0.125$);
- TP_{low} – conservative approach on the calculation of the technical potential, based on Beardsmore et al. [135] ($R = 0.01$).

Although economic issues are not analyzed in this paper, for technological and economic reasons determining the use of hot dry rock technology, for the production of electricity, for the estimation of energy reserves of the K-1 reservoir, the target reservoir lying at a depth of 4.7–5.0 km was taken into account, its thickness is min. 300 m, and the temperature is around 160°C. All the above-listed parameters meet the criteria for EGS summarized in Table 2. Detailed information on the reservoir properties and assumed production parameters, combined with the results of the preliminary reserves assessment, is presented in Table 5.

Other assumptions that were taken into account when calculating reserves considered:

- The influence of radiogenic heat on the thermal regeneration of the rock mass was not considered (radiogenic heat is important for the formation of thermal conditions of the rock mass only in the geological time scale);
- A homogeneous permeability of the fractured zone was assumed (the model was divided into fractures and a rock matrix, but the average value of permeability for the entire structure subjected to hydraulic fracturing was assumed, e.g., a single porosity model instead of dual porosity).

Estimations presented in Table 5 refer to “geobodies” differing in volumes, depths of burden, and petrophysical and thermal parameters. Hence, their direct interpretation does not show which facies (objective) is of the paramount prospectivity. Only in cases when this calculation is converted to a specific value referred to as 1 km³ volume do results become easily comparable. The results of the preliminary calculation of unit geothermal resources in the area of KłECKO anticline are shown in Table 6. In particular, eolian and fluvial complexes of the Rotliegend sediments reveal optimistic estimates of both HIPs and individual types of TPs.

Table 6. Unit geothermal resources of Rotliegend complexes in KłECKO anticline.

Complex	sHIP PJ/km ³	sHIP _e PJ/km ³	sTC PJ/km ³	sTP _{th} MW _e /km ³	sTP _{real} kW _e /km ³	sTP _{low} kW _e /km ³
Playa	345.50	153.95	17.10	18.10	2262.10	180.95
Eolian	386.46	184.17	21.28	22.50	2814.03	225.14
Fluvial	367.90	182.03	21.57	22.81	2849.82	227.97

8. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

The completion of K-1 well, drilled in the central part of the NMT together with the interpretation of a new seismic survey acquired in its vicinity gave a new insight into the geological structure of the KłECKO anticline. In this paper, a new geothermal prospect of deep near-salt geological structures is described. Based on the results of parametric modelling for the Rotliegend EGS reservoir the geothermal potential assessment was run, separately for the playa, eolian and fluvial associations.

The traditional approach to geothermal exploration within the Polish Lowlands is based on cartographic methods, which assume that maps form a synthesis of geological, petrophysical and thermal information atlases (Górecki (ed.), Hajto et al., 2006a;b). Such an approach allows very good regional scale description but creates some radical simplifications. This method, developed in the 1990s, assumes substantial averaging of analyzed parameters as well as assigns thermal conditions to the tops of particular geothermal or stratigraphic complexes. A detailed 3D analysis may result in abundant improvement not only in deep geological structures knowledge but in the quantitative description of the main petrophysical and thermal parameters of the target EGS reservoir. This makes sense when a new data acquisition comprising a new borehole or new seismic has been made. It can be supposed that regional structural-parametric modelling gives satisfactory and optimal solutions. A more detailed analysis of obtained results negates this

statement. A satisfactory modelled regional trend may give good approximation only in these places where the thickness of particular sequences is typical for the entire basin, otherwise, 3D modelling is a must.

Simple calculations show that the deepest fluvial complex characterizes by the highest geothermal reserves, but it should be emphasised that such conclusions are misleading, because it indicates as a prospective one the fluvial complex, resting at 5500 m b.s.l., with average clay content varying about 60% (Table 4), which makes it resistant for long-distance fracturing treatment required by EGS (Table 2).

Considering geothermal potential per volume of rock it should be mentioned that the fluvial complex has similar or even better parameters than the eolian one, but is significantly less porous (avg. 1.76% vs. 4.90% - Table 4) and contains more clay minerals (avg. 60.97% vs. 22.50% - Table 5), which may diminish the effectiveness of hydraulic fracturing. The eolian complex composed of pure sandstones is better for fracturing and rests 300 m shallower which reduces drilling costs. The average porosity of the eolian complex interpreted from well logs (4.9%) is higher than 3%, a minimal requirement for commercial EGS (Table 2). The DST results during the drilling of the K-1 borehole resulted in no flow, which may indicate that in this case interpreted porosity reflects total porosity. The higher content of bound water may favour the eolian complex, because of the high heat capacity of water.

Analyzing thermal parameters of discussed Rotliegend complexes, some attention should be paid to radiogenic heat (RH). Within the sandy Eolian complex, RH varies between 0.5 to 0.75 $\mu\text{W}/\text{m}^3$, and in clay, intercalation reaches up to 1.5 $\mu\text{W}/\text{m}^3$. In comparison, the Fluvial complex presents very high RH values, reaching even 3.4 $\mu\text{W}/\text{m}^3$ (Figure 16). In the case of the presented analysis, radiogenic heat was determined as a function of shale content (VSH). Therefore, high VSH values are not typical for these facies within the Polish Permian Basin (Papiernik et al., 2010). The authors suspect that such a rise of VSH, up to an extreme 72% (Table 4), may result from enrichment in radioactive minerals of volcanogenic origin and does not reflect real shale/clay content in the entire rock masses.

Analysis of the model of thermal gradient distribution within the Rotliegend strata indicates a characteristic distribution of this parameter. The playa complex and the top part of the eolian complex are characterized by a significantly lower thermal gradient (from 1.2 to 2.5°C/100 m) than deeper sequences of the eolian and the fluvial complexes (from 2.5 to 3.5°C/100 m). A similar cooling effect observed at the base of salt structures has been widely described (Selig & Wallick, 1966; Fuchs & Förster, 2010; Daniilidis & Herber, 2017). It is related to intensive heat transfer through high-conductive Zechstein evaporites (Fuchs & Förster, 2010). The distribution of the thermal anomalies (thermal gradient) within and around salt structures depends on their shape, but independent of the shape, all salt structures act as a channel for vertical heat transfer. The changes in temperature gradients are proportional to the thickness of the salt sequence and the shape of the salt intrusion Daniilidis & Herber, 2017).

Analysis of the average heat flow also indicates visible thermal anomalies related to salt structures. Average heat flow at ground level within the Polish Permian Basin varies about 71 mW/m^2 (Szewczyk & Gientka, 2009; Majorowicz & Grad, 2020), in comparison within the German Permian Basin which varies about 63 mW/m^2 , and in the area of the K-1 well, according to Majorowicz & Grad (2020), reaches 74 mW/m^2 , while the heat flow determined in the K-1 equal to ca. 84 mW/m^2 . This indicates that the K-1 well is located within a local positive thermal anomaly. The Kłęcko Anticline has the form of a salt pillow. This type of shape has the most preferable, from a geothermal exploration point of view, thermal properties distribution.

Furthermore, in areas with a significant salt thickness (over several hundred meters, e.g., in the Polish Lowlands), detailed 3D models can identify the presence of appropriate conditions for the production of geothermal energy. Finally, the overlapping of thick salt layers, a suitable aquifer and demand for geothermal heat could outline favourable locations for geothermal development. The discussed methodology for assessing the geothermal potential is an important step towards the effective use of low-permeability (EGS) reservoirs for power generation or direct applications. The analysis presented above allowed the authors to draw the following conclusions:

- Regional scale 3D models can be used as a more precise tool for geothermal exploration than commonly applied solutions based on simple cartographic techniques;
- Salt structures are potential objectives for geothermal exploration. The positive thermal anomalies at the top and above salt structures are a result of the high thermal conductivity of salt. They may be emphasized by contact with low-conductive rocks, e.g., claystones;
- The changes in the thermal gradient are proportional to the salt thickness; the shape of the salt intrusion is also important;
- In Poland over ~100 salt structures have been mapped, and a number of them may meet the criteria of being interesting objectives for geothermal exploration mentioned in Table 2;
- Further research of the Paleozoic formations is necessary for a better understanding of high-temperature resources and to indicate new opportunities for geothermal development in regions outside the areas of proven geothermal potential hosted in Mesozoic formations of the Polish Lowlands;
- Regional- to local-scale 3D models are very valuable for planning a deep geothermal installation. Because of the heterogeneity of the subsurface, basin geometry (especially around salt structures) and thermal properties, temperatures may deviate from the average geothermal gradient trend;
- The proposed methodology appears to be justified when a new well data set is used to verify 3D geological models in the salt structure zones. In particular, the discussed methods and models can be used to refine existing geothermal potential maps or to calibrate 3D parametric models used to assess both conventional and unconventional (EGS) geothermal potential;
- The general applicability of the proposed methodology makes it of interest for a broad range of applications in geothermal utilization as well as for CCS issues.

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